

READING IN THE AGE OF INSTAGRAM-IFICATION: TECHNAURITURE AS A CATALYST FOR A REVITALISING READING CULTURE

Simphiwe Mpho Zondani

Independent Institute of Education's Varsity College, Humanities and Social Science, South Africa,
szondani@varsitycollege.co.za

Abstract

The emergence of the South African reading crisis has prompted many critical discussions around the dire state of reading and literacy in our country and has evoked further consideration around what interventions can be enacted to reinvigorate local reading culture. The local reading crisis also offers a moment of critical reflection upon what exactly is meant by the words 'reading,' 'reading culture' and 'literacy' and how current definitions are firmly-rooted in book culture, ignoring the value of other literary forms, particularly oral forms which are very relevant to a multicultural and multilingual South African milieu. To foster a more open and inclusive kind of reading culture these definitions must be problematised. To this end, this paper will utilise the 'technauriture paradigm' first advanced by Kaschula (2011) to critically explore emergent digital literary forms such as The New York Public Library's InstaNovels to examine how these texts may offer salient insights into how digital technologies are challenging and reconfiguring reading habits and thinking around, and in turn effecting a different kind of reading culture.

Keywords: technauriture, digitality, instanovels, reading, literacy

1. INTRODUCTION

In "Ending the Reading Wars: Reading Acquisition from Novice to Expert," Castles, Rustle and Nation (2016) assert the importance of reading, defining it as the basis of knowledge acquisition. Their definition not only underscores the significance of the activity, it places reading as the process through which one contends with texts and access the information contained therein. This formulation of reading as an essential activity required to acquire knowledge is one which is echoed by Okwonkwo (2004), who positions it as an indispensable activity and tool for empowerment. Effiong (2016: 1) extends this relationship, going on to define the figure or subject who reads as one who is able to reason, think, imagine, discriminate, interpret and draw inferences.

Despite the recognized importance of reading and literacy, UNESCO asserts that it is one of the most neglected of all the Education for all goals, adopted by the Dakar Framework (2000); particularly in terms of public policy and political attention (UNESCO 2008). This is not to say that there has been no improvement in global literacy rates. According to the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, global literacy rates increased from 56% in 1950 to 70% in 1980, 75% in 1990 and 82% between 2000 and 2004. But there are still great strides

to be made.

Despite the rapid increments, the distribution of the illiterate population has not changed. In fact, the remaining 28%, which represent approximately 774 million people – almost a fifth of the world’s population—is located in the global South, specifically in South and West Asia, sub-Saharan Africa, East Asia and the Pacific (UNESCO 2008).

1.2 Framing of the South African Reading Crisis in local media

Much of the media discourse around the South African Reading crisis generates from the results of the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS); a standardized literacy assessment that comparatively analyses literacy rates and trends in literacy development across 50 countries across the globe. The study is conducted over 5-year intervals among learners in grade 4.

The results of the most recent PIRLS conducted in 2016, revealed that there had been no improvement in the overall local literacy scores in South Africa since the previous one conducted in 2011 (Howie et al. 2017: 11). This resulted in South Africa ranking last out of the 50 participating countries (Howie et al. 2017: 11). The study report further revealed that 78% of the assessed student were unable to meet the Low International Benchmark of literacy compared to only 4% internationally, which indicates that a majority of the local sample are unable to “read for meaning or retrieve basic information from the text to answer simplistic questions” (Howie et al. 2017: 4).

Following the publishing of these results, local literacy rates became an immediate cause celebre among local news outlets, with many uprightly declaring a national reading crisis; proclaiming the ‘dire state of’ local reading culture while some while The Conversation opted for a more sensationalistic angle, raising it from a mere ‘reading crisis’ to a ‘cognitive catastrophe’ (Aitchison 2016; Rule and Land 2017).

This crisis-centric discourse continued into later representations of the issues, and eventually even infiltrated political discourse. This is quite evident in President Cyril Ramaphosa’s latest State of The Nation Address delivered early 2020, where he referenced the reading crisis in a manner which echoed many of the news reports preceding it, making specific reference to the plight of 10 years old not knowing how to read – which is in reference to the oft quoted statistic lifted from the PIRLS 2016 study. This is also evident in the title of a recent webinar hosted by the South African Literacy Association, which referenced the South African reading issue as “The Other Pandemic”.

Interestingly, while there are numerous other studies considering the state of literacy and book reading in South Africa, most notably the National Book Council’s ‘National survey into the reading and book reading behavior of adult South Africans’ (2016) published in the same year, the results of the 2016 PIRLS remain the most emphasized. These highlight the crucial issue of framing within the news coverage of the reading crisis. The import and power of news media, particularly with regards to perception is highlighted by Tuchman (cited in Ardèvol-Abreu 2015), who describes it using the metaphor of a window, whose frame limits the perception of reality. From this formulation, according to (Entman, cited in Ardèvol-Abreu 2015: 424), framing can then be defined as “a process in which some aspects of reality are selected, and given greater emphasis or importance, so that the problem is defined, its causes are diagnosed, moral judgments are suggested, and appropriate solutions and actions are proposed”.

Thus, the inclusion of only the 2016 PIRLS report can be read as a deliberate act of framing and agenda-setting by the media, which limits the scope of the critical discussions around reading and literacy in South Africa by focusing on the imperative issue of literacy rates among children, leaving the equally important issue of adult illiteracy and poor reading habit among adult and adolescents unattended.

In response to this formulation of the reading crisis, there has been a pronounced a rehashing of what can be termed ‘post-literary panic’ which appears to repurpose earlier arguments for the death of the book, or the death of literature as seen in seminal texts like Sven Birkirts’ Guttenberg’s Elegies and in McLuhan’s Guttenberg’s Galaxy, where he advances the somewhat technologically-determinist idea that following the ‘Electronic Age’ – the invention of New Media – we will settle into an age of secondary orality – a phenomenon first identified by his fellow Canadian School counterpart, Walter Ong, in Literacy and Orality. Secondary Orality, according to Ong, has a basis in written culture and print, but sees heavier usage of the ‘oral’ and sonic, as seen in the prominence of news and radio during his time. Evident within this line of thinking is the underlying ‘displacement model’ explanation, where upon the arrival of a new medium or media, older media lose prominence and import. This is reflective of a growing perspective inspired by the

ideal of displacement rather than a complementary media model, where various media converge and produce new rhizomatic kinds of engagements. These two perspectives are unpacked below.

2. CONVERGENCE AND DISPLACEMENT PERSPECTIVES

The advent and consequent popularity of a new medium often evokes fears of the displacement of existent media by the incoming one. This often results in the dissemination of an apocalyptic type of discourse chronicling the 'death of' said medium or communication technology at the hands of its predecessor (Nguyen and Western 2006: 64). In fact, Nguyen and Western (2006) note that, at the time of publishing their article, a Google search returned "899 documents with the keyword phrase 'death of print', 368 with 'death of television' and [...] 4360 with 'death of radio'" at the hands of the newer medium of the Internet (2006:64). However, as noted by Twenge and Spitzer, in their study on the trends in adolescent media use, it is unclear whether time spent on digital media has replaced time spent on older forms of media or merely supplemented it (2019: 330). While some scholars (Bauerlein 2007; De Waal & Schoenbach 2010; Ha & Fang 2012; Kayany & Yelsma, 2000; Lee & Lee, 2015; Lee & Leung 2008), have argued for the former, there are also other who advance the latter (Dienlin, Masur, & Trepte 2017; Robinson & Martin 2009; Vergeer & Pelzer 2009).

The two academic perspectives draw from two distinct models of media use, namely media displacement model (Bauerlein 2007; McComb 1972) and complementary model (Dutta-Bergman 2004; Nguyen & Western 2006). According to Twenge and Spitzberg, the displacement model has two primary forms—functional and chronemic (2019: 332). Function displacement, it is argued, is predicated on an either an "individual-difference" or a media-based explanation; the former hypothesizes that the incoming medium performs a function previously fulfilled by its predecessor, thereby resulting in its displacement (Twenge & Spitzberg 2019: 332). As an illustrative example, books and magazines are positioned as older media whose principal entertainment function may be displaced by the arrival of online site and games (2019: 332).

On the other hand, the media-use explanation relies on the perceived benefits and advancements offered by the new media form in relation to the older one; here the example of digital media is used and argued to fulfill existing needs and expectation "better and more enjoyably than older media" (Newell et al., cited in Twenge & Spitzberg 2019: 332).

The second type of displacement model chronemic perspective is described relies on previous formulations of the attention economy (Ciampaglia, Flammini, & Menczer, 2015; Huberman & Wu, 2008; Jang & Pasek, 2015; Simon, 1971; Wagner, 2015; Webster, 2014) and advances time as a limited resource that precipitates a competitive media ecology where one medium is selected in lieu of another (Twenge & Spitzer 2019:332).

Complimentary theory is positioned in opposition to its subtractive counterpart. Rather than assert the privileging of a particular for of media over another, this model posits that an incoming medium may have the capacity to co-exist alongside older media, even functioning as a complement to them (Twenge & Spitzer 2019: 334). In many ways, this complementary model or theory is more in line with more contemporary thinking in media and news media, which advances the concept of convergence rather than displacement. With this convergent perspective in mind, the notion of a singular form of 'literacy' versus a multiliteracy perspective is explored below.

3. CONVERGENCE AND DISPLACEMENT PERSPECTIVES

Referencing academic literature on literacy, Walter (2010) contends that there is often a tendency to ascribe various consequences for literacy without initially defining what 'literacy' actually means. Admittedly, this is not a simple task. Scholars acknowledge the great difficulty and complexity of defining exactly what the term entails (Roberts, 1995; Bernardo 2000; Maposa and Wasserman, 2009). However, this is not true only for scholars who research the consequences of literacy. Keefe and Copeland (2011) note that many studies considering approaches to teaching literacy mention the concept or the relation of reading/writing without explicitly defining what is denoted when the terms are applied.

Some academics have provided reasons for the oversight, suggesting the ever-changing, protean nature of the concept as one of the major reasons for this occurrence (Roberts, 1995; Bernardo 2000; Maposa and Wasserman, 2009). Mkandawire (2018) echoes this perspective, noting the difficulties of defining literacy in a contemporary context owing to the polysemy and multitude of interpretations or perceptions associated with the term. This was also recognized by UNESCO, who also indicated dynamism of concept and the multiplicity of meanings that continue to be ascribed to the concept (UNESCO, 2008).

Due to this multiplicity and constant evolutions, Roberts (1995) asserts that many literacy definitions were advanced by various stakeholders such as scholars and adult literacy specialists over the past fifty years. Mkandawire (2018) notes that these definitions often appear different in terms of orientation but display a similar focus. According to Edwards and Potts (2008) these definitions are generally more conventional and often focus on technical skills aligned with schooling academic progression; namely, reading and writing. This technical focus is echoed by UNESCO, whose definition underscores tangible skills, specifically reading and writing (UNESCO, 2006).

It is important to note that UNESCO's definition was subject to change over the years. In fact, this definition has also been subject to evolution over time. In 1958, their definition simply encompasses reading and writing a short simple statement on their daily life (UNESCO 2008). With the establishment of the Experimental World Literacy Program in 1966, this definition evolves into a more functional definition. This coincides with the emergence of functional literacy in the 1960s. The new definition becomes linked to the realm of productivity and thus includes "all those activities in which literacy is required for effective functioning" and enables one to continue to use reading, writing, and calculation" for the development of their community (UNESCO, 2008: 18).

In 2005, this conceptualization evolves further and is described as "the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate and compute using printed and written materials associated with varying contexts" (UNESCO, 2008). During this time, it also comes to include the function of enabling one to reach goals and participate in broader society (UNESCO, 2008).

In a review article titled "Literacy and Literacies," Collins (1995:75) recognizes that studies on literacy often present dichotomies such as "literate vs illiterate, written vs spoken, educated vs uneducated, modern vs traditional". The first of these dichotomies—literate vs illiterate—is often invoked in initial conceptualizations of literacy. In many ways, this is influenced by the linguistic origins of the word itself. Etymologically, both pairs derive from the Latin root, *litteratus*, a term used by Cicero to describe a learned person (NACAE, 1989). During the middle Ages in Europe, the term came to be used to describe one who could read Latin, a skill required to interpret common law and the Bible. Over time, this binarial construction came to be contested and cast as simplistic (Martinez and Fernandez, 2010). Other critiques suggested that binarial conceptualization of the terms gave rise to certain value judgments such as identify whether one is literate, or illiterate, thereby producing a particular connotations (Scribner, 1984).

This illustrates what Roberts (1995) claims when he asserts that defining literacy is more than a case of competing definitions and conceptualizations, but as a case of political contestation (1995: 413). Wickert (1992) offers a similar view, arguing that this issue of competing definitions and constructs also involves broader concerns around inclusion and exclusion. The categorization of who is considered either literate or illiterate, and the resultant rates and indices derived from this arise from the definition or construction of literacy (Wickert 1992: 30). Therefore, in Wickert's view, arguments over literacy are arguments over whose construction and, relatedly, whose politics prevails (1992:30).

This observation is echoed by the National Advisory Council on Adult Education (1978:2) asserts that the task of defining literacy is more than one of mere definition, rather it is concerned with the "aspirational, psychological, educational, and political intentions" of the term. The term is described as an auto-positive term much like liberty, justice, and happiness, which are argued to be assumed to be simple owing to their simple, almost primal qualities that are "necessary" and "desirable" within our culture (1978:2).

This idealized conception of literacy beyond what can be empirically measured to constitute it veers into the realm of what is often described as a literacy myth (Graff, 1979; Graff, 1987). Scholars characterize this so-called myth as the belief that "the acquisition of literacy is a necessary precursor to and invariably results in economic, democratic practice, cognitive enhancement, and upward social mobility" (Graff and Duffy, 2014: np). This reflects what Scribner identifies when he asserts that despite multiple efforts to concretely measure and define literacy, these formulations reflect a certain sense of moral elevation and a purported state of grace.

Graff and Duffy (2014) argue that this perspective is not a novel one and has been repeatedly expressed throughout the Renaissance and Reformation, then again during the Enlightenment, where it was associated with notions of "progress, order, transformation and control" (2014: 32). Linked to this perspective is the conviction that none of these associated qualities can be attained via any other means, rather literacy remains the most vital of variables (Graff and Duffy, 2014). When considered in their entirety, these attitudes cumulatively characterize the "literacy myth" (Graff and Duffy, 2014; Graff, 1979; Graff, 1987).

Graff and Duffy (2014) further assert that the myth is often adopted by many researchers in the field as well as commentators. It is also purported to be reflected in popular contemporary discourses, notably book sponsorship initiatives, and celebrity-led reading campaigns by organizations linking the acquisition of the skill to other self-esteem, parenting skills, and social mobility. A major issue with this widespread adoption, identified by Graff and Duffy (2014) is how it begins its capacity to shape public and expert opinion, policymakers, and institutions concerned with international developmental work.

Another way in which certain literacy myths persist is the continued invocation of the singular 'Literacy' in assertions of its decline, despite the emergence and proliferation of other literacies. With the emergence of these novel technologies, there are attempts to extend the applicability of literacy as a term beyond its standard relation to the written word (Buckingham, 2015). Buckingham (2015) traces these efforts to as early as the 1980s, referencing the work of Margaret Meek Spencer, who is responsible for developing the concept of emergent literacies to describe young children's media-related play.

According to Maposa and Wasserman (2009), this shift towards breadth in terms of literacy definitions becomes solidified in the 1990s, where it is no longer only applicable to the field of language but is broadened to include other competencies. Consequently, this results in the proliferation of multiple literacies, thereby destabilizing the cultural cachet and privilege of the singular invocation of the concept (Furedi, 2015). While a myriad of literacies is likely to exist, Furedi (2015) identifies the following emergent ones:

visual literacy, aural literacy, computer literacy, emotional literacy, sexual literacy, ecoliteracy, media literacy, media literacy, multicultural literacy, and financial literacy.

These new forms he argues, call into question the previously attested uniqueness and authority of the singular conception of 'Literacy' (Furedi, 2015:12). This representation of this 'Literacy' as a single form of literacy amongst many, he further adds, renders it banal (2015:12). However, Furedi's (2015) perspective is not shared by all. As scholars like Buckingham (2015) offer an interesting critique of these proliferations, suggesting that they create confusion regarding the original meaning of literacy as a concept. To support this perspective, references are made to popular discussions of economic literacy, emotional literacy, and spiritual literacy. When applied beyond the written word, he asserts, literacy itself becomes vague and synonymous with the idea of competence or skill.

Despite the growing multiplicity of 'literacies', the narrow, singular usage of literacy retains its privilege and primacy; as evidenced by Castles, Rustle, and Nation's (2016) assertion that reading is the basis of knowledge acquisition. Their definition underscores the significance of the activity and places reading as the process through which one contends with texts and accesses the information contained therein. This formulation of reading as an essential activity required to acquire knowledge is echoed by Okwonkwo (2004), who positions it as an indispensable activity and tool for empowerment. Effiong (2016: 1) extends this relationship, going on to define the figure or subject who reads as one who can reason, think, imagine, discriminate, interpret, and draw inferences.

This linking of logical and rational faculties to the advent of writing technologies, reading, and literacy does not begin with recent scholars like Effiong (2016), but can be traced back to the work of a formative scholar and influential within Literacy Studies, Professor Walter Ong, whose seminal text, *Orality and Literacy: Technologizing the Word* (1982) is a mainstay within scholarly discussions on the subject of the changing role of literacy and its impact on society and civilization (Baumann, 1986: 2).

As Baumann notes, Professor Ong's work builds upon a body of existing academic literature, namely earlier studies of Renaissance thought and rhetoric, and extends existent pioneering ideas advanced by scholars like Harold Innis (1950), Lord (1960), fellow Toronto School thinkers McLuhan (1962), Goody (1968), Parry (1971) and Havelock (1972) (1986). In *Orality and Literacy* (1982), Ong underscores the emergence of a written linguistic script and marks it as a "momentous departure" from what he terms primary orality and the social structures which underpin it. He further argues that the chirographic culture, which follows, is closely aligned with the practices of handwriting, and, in turn, the typographic culture of print. The arrival of print, Ong argues, is highly consequential and fundamental to the reorientation of human perception and thought (Baumann, 1986). In fact, this central proposition by Ong is captured in one of the oft-cited phrases from the text, writing is a technology that restructures thought (Ong, 1986; Ong, 1982). That is, as Baumann observes, writing is not a mere external tool but "a practice that alters human consciousness to the degree to which it is, as Walter Ong says, 'interiorized' (1986). Writing, Ong further proposes, takes language from the ephemera of speech, and fixes it within time, as written signs and thereby objects in space (Baumann 1986). Further consequences of this separation, which he calls 'diagnosis', are the removal of thought from what is

immediate, personal, social, and cultural, therefore allowing a degree of separation of “knowledge from interpretation, logic from rhetoric...of cumulative learning from the judgement and wisdom acquired from experience” (Baumann, 1986).

However, as Baumann cautions, this perspective is not without its pitfalls. In fact, the discourse around literacy, particularly the reference to its potentialities, consequences, and effects is criticized and countered by Brian Street, who suggests that such a view implies that literacy is an independent variable, an autonomous entity unto itself (cited in Baumann, 1986: 12). Contra this position, Street exposes the ethnocentrism and ideological biases which belie this perspective and draws specific attention to the circular nature of its logic and its “self-validating equation of literacy and Western varieties of rational thought and define literacy ... as the source of rationality (ibid).

Rather than advance this detached ideal of literacy, Street proposes an understanding which considers the socio-cultural factors that inform the use and function of literacy, such as stratification, power differentials, and ideological hegemony (cited in Baumann, 1986: 13). This is of specific importance for the African continent and much of the global South as the arrival of literacy is intimately related to the phenomenon of colonialism and cultural imperialism.

For Street, literacy can therefore not be discussed as a unified phenomenon but as a variable social practice (Baumann, 1986: 13). As such, Street forgoes the singular term ‘literacy’ and more appropriately refers to the more polysemic plural ‘literacies’ (Street, 1984: 8). This shift, in many ways, echoes more recent discursive shifts within Literacy Studies where the advent and popularity of various communication and digital technologies have had an incredible impact and given rise to the recognition of various other media-related literacies such as media-literacy, digital literacies, and multiliteracies.

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